

EFFECT OF FIBRE ORIENTATIONS ON PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE OF NOTCHED $[\theta/0^\circ/-\theta/90^\circ]_s$ COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Notched coupon tests are routinely performed to determine limiting design envelopes for damage tolerant structures in aircraft. Typically, a large number of tests are required, resulting in considerable expense in time and resources. Better and more accurate analysis tools with the ability to model dominant failure mechanisms could mean that some potential cases could be interrogated and screened by virtual tests instead. In this study, a series of $[\theta/0^\circ/-\theta/90^\circ]_s$ OHT laminates with fibre orientation θ varied from 0° to 90° was tested to failure and the corresponding computational progressive failure analysis was carried out for each case. The finite element model was constructed using three-dimensional continuum shell elements and cohesive elements, and analysed with user-defined subroutines in the software Abaqus. Damage in the elements was modelled by degrading the stiffness according to an energy-based criterion and linear softening law.

1 INTRODUCTION

The open-hole tension (OHT) strength of laminated composites has often been used as a limiting criterion in damage tolerance design of aircraft structures. Despite the seemingly simple problem, OHT for composite material is still a challenging problem because failure in fiber reinforced composites involves complex mechanisms such as multiple matrix yielding and cracking, fiber breakage and pull out, and delamination. Furthermore, the OHT strength and dominant failure modes depends on dimensions such as hole diameter, specimen width, stacking sequence and thickness [1].

Chen et.al [2] and Ridha et. al [3] have shown that finite element (FE) method with damage progression modelling capabilities is a good alternative for predicting OHT of composite material as they can be used to predict various laminate design without relying to the property of the laminate itself, e.g. the laminate strength and toughness. Major failure modes seen in experiments [4, 5] such as matrix damage, fiber breakage, and interface delamination can be modelled using this FE method. They found that delamination and ply thickness has to be considered in order to get a good prediction. These studies, however, were limited to modelling quasi-isotropic laminates or laminates that is made of the traditional 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, and 90° plies.

This study will present a progressive damage finite element method for composite laminates that only the ply-level and interlaminar properties of the composite. The method is based mainly on the previous study by Ridha et al. [3]. OHT tests of anisotropic carbon fiber reinforced plastic composite laminated are compared with the predictions obtained from finite element simulations.

2 EXPERIMENT

Laminated fiber reinforced composites were made from IM7/MTM-45 carbon epoxy pre-pregs, processed at 177 °C and 550 kPa. The layup was $[\theta/0^\circ/-\theta/90^\circ]_s$ with eight different values of θ : 0°, 10°, 20°, 30°, 45°, 60°, and 90°. Each ply has a nominal thickness of 0.137 mm. Specimens of 38.1 mm wide with 6.35 mm hole in the middle (

Figure 1) were then cut from these laminates for the OHT tests. Three to five specimens were tested for each of the composite lamina resulting in the open-hole tensile strength data and photographs depicting the failure pattern after the test.

Figure 1 OHT specimen

3 DAMAGE MODELLING STRATEGY

A progressive damage model for fiber reinforced composite material should ideally be able to cover all of the main damage modes that can occur in the actual material which includes in plane fiber or matrix damage and delamination. In this study, Tsai-Wu [6] and maximum stress criterion are used to determine the initiation of matrix and fiber failure. In plane fiber or matrix dominated damages are then modelled using the smeared crack model in which the fiber direction stiffness E_{11} , transverse direction stiffness E_{22} , shear stiffness E_{22} and Poisson's ratio ν_{12} are degraded using the following equations:

$$E_{11} = (1 - d_f)E_{11_0} \quad (1)$$

$$E_{22} = (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)E_{22_0} \quad (2)$$

$$G_{12} = (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)G_{12_0} \quad (3)$$

$$G_{12} = (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)G_{12_0} \quad (4)$$

$$\nu_{12} = (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)\nu_{12_0} \quad (5)$$

In these equations, subscript 0 refers to the undamaged state, while d_f and d_m are respectively the degradation factor due to fiber and matrix dominated damage. The value of d_f and d_m increases from 0 to nearly 1 as the damage progresses in an element.

Similarly, once a quadratic stress criterion is satisfied, interface delamination is modelled using the stiffness degradation method applied to cohesive elements between the composite plies in which its normal stiffness (K_{nn}) and shear stiffness (K_{ss} and K_{tt}) are reduced using the following equations:

$$K_{nn} = (1 - d_c)K_{nn_0} \quad (6)$$

$$K_{ss} = (1 - d_c)K_{ss_0} \quad (7)$$

$$K_{tt} = (1 - d_c)K_{tt_0} \quad (8)$$

Details of the damage initiation criteria for the composite ply and interface and its progression scheme are explained by Ridha et al. [3].

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The OHT specimens were modelled in Abaqus 6.11-1 [7] using three dimensional continuum shell elements for the composite plies and cohesive elements for the interfaces. Damage models are applied to the model using a user defined subroutine UMAT. Continuum elements with the size of 0.5 mm × 0.5 mm are used in the midsection of the model where the main damages are expected.

As shown Figure 2 two types of element mesh were made in this study: a. aligned mesh and b. non-aligned mesh. In the aligned mesh model, the element sides are all aligned to the loading and the transverse direction except for the ones adjacent to the circular hole. On the other hand, element in the non-aligned mesh models are allowed to have various orientation.

Figure 2 Finite element model of an OHT specimen: a. aligned mesh and b. non-aligned mesh

Progressive damage models are prone to convergence problems. The introduction of material softening model with negative tangent modulus in the finite element model often result in an unstable simulation in which an extended amount of time is needed to find a converged solution or a converged solution cannot be found. Following Ridha et al. [3], the linear softening law used in the composite plies and cohesive elements is approached by using a zigzagging softening model in order to alleviate the convergence problem . As shown in Figure 3.a, the stress-displacement curve is allowed to deviate within a certain band from the linear softening curve by degrading the stiffness in a stepwise manner (Figure 3. b). In these models the maximum deviation is set to be 5 % of the strength. This zigzagging approach stabilises the model by eliminating the ill condition problem of having a negative tangent modulus. Furthermore, this zigzagging approach also simplifies the non-linear finite element problem by reducing the need to modify the element stiffness in every iterations because the stiffness becomes piecewise constant.

Figure 3 Zigzag approximations of a linear softening law (a) and its corresponding stiffness degradation (b)

Table 1 shows the properties used in modelling the composite plies while Table 2 shows the properties of the interface. The stiffness, Poisson's ratio, and strength values of the composite plies are calibrated from tensile and compressive tests. The fiber/longitudinal direction fracture toughness is assumed to be similar to the IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy material presented by Laffan et al. [8] who used compact tension specimens to obtain this value. The interface fracture toughness's are obtained from the study by Barikani, Saidpour and Sezen [9, 10] who obtained the values using double cantilever beam and end notched flexure tests, while its strengths are assumed to be the same as the transverse direction normal and shear strength of the composite plies. The transverse direction fracture toughness's are assumed to be the same as the interface fracture toughness's. The value of η are assumed based on the study by Camanho et al. [11] who presented the interfacial toughness properties of IM7/977-2 carbon/epoxy system.

Table 1 Composite ply properties

Property	Value
Longitudinal tensile X_t (MPa)	2500
Longitudinal compression X_c (MPa)	1700
Transverse tensile Y_t (MPa)	69
Transverse compression Y_c (MPa)	169
Longitudinal shear S_{12} (MPa)	43
Longitudinal stiffness E_{11} (GPa)	175
Transverse stiffness E_{22} (GPa)	8.2
Shear stiffness G_{12} (GPa)	5.5
Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	0.33
Longitudinal toughness G_{fc} (kJ/m ²)	147.2
Transverse normal toughness G_{nc} (kJ/m ²)	0.372
Transverse shear toughness G_{sc} (kJ/m ²)	1.192
η	1.39

Table 2 Interfacial cohesive properties

Property	Value
Normal strength N (MPa)	69
Shear strength S (MPa)	43
Normal toughness G_n (kJ/m ²)	0.372
Shear toughness G_s (kJ/m ²)	1.192
η	1.39

It should be noted that the fiber direction fracture toughness of thick or blocked plies is assumed to increase linearly with thickness due to the study by Laffan et al. [12] who shows that fibre direction fracture toughness of a composite ply increases as more 0-ply are blocked together because of the larger number of fiber pull-outs. Their data shows that the fiber direction toughness of two plies blocked together is about twice of the single ones. Following Chen et al. [2], in this study, the 90° plies in the middle of the composite layups and the 0° plies in the $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ]_s$ layup is considered as thick/blocked plies and hence their longitudinal fracture toughness is set to be twice and thrice of the other plies, respectively.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the OHT strength predicted by the finite element models compared to the experimental results. The figure shows that the aligned mesh models are able to accurately predict the OHT strength of every layup while the non-aligned mesh model performs fairly well except in the case of the $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ]_s$ and $[10^\circ, 0^\circ, -10^\circ, 90^\circ]_s$ layup. The OHT strength predicted by the non-aligned mesh model values for the $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ]_s$ layup is about 27 % lower than the experimental values. This can be explained by examining the failure pattern shown in the experiment and compare it with the model prediction. As shown in Figure 5, these $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ]_s$ and $[10^\circ, 0^\circ, -10^\circ, 90^\circ]_s$ layup show fiber splitting elongated in the loading direction upon failure. This type of fiber splitting which results in a very high shear deformation cannot be modelled correctly using elements that are randomly oriented because of the inherent mechanical behaviour of the elements in which shear deformation is always coupled with normal stresses. Therefore, elements that have failed by matrix shear failure are still able to transfer shear load due to the presence of undegraded fiber direction

stiffness E_{11} . Figure 6 shows that although the non-aligned mesh is able to predict the presence of elongated splitting, the model cannot correctly model the big reduction in stress concentration due to fiber splitting in the 0° plies and hence this model predict a much lower OHT strength. On the other hand, mesh alignment with fiber orientation decouples the shear deformation and the normal stresses. Therefore, the aligned-mesh model is able to correctly capture the behaviour of fiber splitting correctly and shows a big reduction of stress concentration upon fiber splitting in the 0° plies.

Figure 4 Strength predictions for $[\theta/0^\circ/-\theta/90^\circ]_s$ laminates

Figure 5 Fiber splitting in $[0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ and $[10^\circ/0^\circ/-10^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ layups

Figure 6 Fiber splitting and its effect on stress concentration of each model

Besides OHT strength prediction, the simulations also results in predictions on the failure pattern of the OHT specimens. Predicted damage pattern for $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 45^\circ$ are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8. The failure patterns in the models correlate very well with the experimental results; the following features signify their agreements:

- For laminate $[0^\circ / 0^\circ / 0^\circ / 90^\circ]_s$:
 - Fiber failure in the 0° plies propagates vertically, perpendicular to the loading direction, while matrix failures in this plies are elongated in the loading direction implying fiber splitting by shear.
 - Failure in the 90° ply is dominated by matrix failure which started from the edge of the hole in the vertical direction implying fiber splitting.
- For laminate $[45^\circ / 0^\circ / 45^\circ / 90^\circ]_s$:
 - The main crack initially propagates vertically, perpendicular to the loading direction, and then changes its direction to 45° after cutting through nearly half of the ligament.
 - Matrix failure in the $\pm 45^\circ$ spreads along the main crack
 - Delamination between the plies spreads around the area of matrix and fiber failure.

Figure 7 Failure map of $[0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate

Figure 8 Failure map of $[45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate

6 CONCLUSIONS

Previous study by Chen et al. [2] and Ridha et al. [3] have shown that finite element method with progressive damage algorithm can be used to effectively predict the OHT strength of quasi-isotropic composite laminate or laminate that is made of the traditional 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, and 90° plies. They emphasized that the key ingredients for these simulations to work is the inclusion of in-plane lamina damage modelling, delamination modelling and the correct value of fiber direction fracture toughness especially when there is ply blocking. This study generalize the conclusion further by showing that the same approach also works very well in predicting the OHT strength of anisotropic laminate consisting of plies in various orientation. This shows that virtual OHT tests on laminated composite can now be confidently performed and hence laminate design and optimization can be done prior to

fabrication. It should however be noted that progressive failure damage model using smeared crack model with random element orientation cannot correctly model elongated fiber splitting that results in large shear deformation. Elements that are aligned to the fiber direction should be used for such cases.

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